

ISAJ

INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

Vol. 10 Issue: 1 | April, 2025

ISAJ NEWSLETTER

An Initiative of ISAJ

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Will be held on November 28-29, 2025, in Shizuoka city.

Watch for announcement on the website and mailing list.

<https://isaj.jp>

From Editor's Desk

Greetings and a warm welcome to the first issue of ISAJ Newsletter in 2025! Our apologies for the delay.

In this issue, we bring you a new feature “From Counsellor’s Desk,” in which Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India in Tokyo, brief us on important developments in the field science and education between India and Japan. We present you with two research articles, as well as an event report and a photo gallery on the ISAJ Hokkaido Symposium 2024 held in December of the last year.

In the Counsellor’s Desk, Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar updates us on recently forged partnerships between Indian and Japanese institutions, this being the India–Japan Year of Science, Technology & Innovation Exchange (2025–26).

The Research Spotlight is on novel nonlinear optical phenomena in quantum materials which is a very relevant topic in this century with the advent of the quantum revolution. This timely article by Dr. Babu Baijnath Prasad briefly explores nonlinear optical effects, such as second-harmonic generation and bulk photovoltaic effects, and how they can be tuned by applied external fields which can have potential real-world applications in multiferroic photovoltaics and spintronics.

The Research Highlight is on a Ni superalloy (which can retain strength at very high temperatures) Inconel 718. It is used in jet engines, and are subjected to fatigue due to cyclic stress during use, leading to failure. Mohit Ludhwani’s Ph.D. work involves studying the fatigue behavior experimentally and modeling to predict the fatigue response.

In a first, the Hokkaido Chapter organized ISAJ Hokkaido 2024 symposium on December 13, 2024, in the Hokkaido University Sapporo campus. See Event Report page and the Photo gallery. ISAJ again reached a milestone with this symposium. This was a first regional symposium of ISAJ. With rapidly increasing graduate students and young scientists from India, each region can have a one day symposium each year, similar to the main symposium.

We hope you would find the present issue of our Newsletter interesting. We look forward to receiving your feedback. Any suggestions/ideas for improving the upcoming newsletters are welcome.

Editor(s)
Alok Singh
Aaditya Manjanath

India–Japan Year of Science, Technology & Innovation Exchange (2025–26): A Shared Vision for a Transformative Future

Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar

Counsellor (S&T),
Embassy of India, Tokyo
cst.tokyo@mea.gov.in

Dr. Panwar is Counsellor, Science and Technology, at Embassy of India in Tokyo. He is a Ph.D. from IIT Delhi in Intellectual Property and Standards. He has been a senior scientist at Technology Information Forecasting and Assessment Council, New Delhi.

In this column he will update us on important developments in the field of science and education between India and Japan.

India, under the transformative vision of Honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modi ji during the Amrit Kaal, is taking a major leap toward becoming a developed nation—Viksit Bharat—by 2047. Science, technology, and innovation (STI) have been accorded top priority in recent policy initiatives. Landmark steps such as allocating Rs 1 lakh crore (1 trillion) to the Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), the launch of the BioE3 Policy, and others initiatives in quantum, AI and cyber physical systems etc shows India's commitment to interdisciplinary translational STI efforts.

In this context, the India–Japan partnership holds special significance, as the two nations enjoy a “Special Strategic and Global Partnership.” Following the success of the past two years designated as the India–Japan Years of Tourism under the theme *#ConnectingHimalayaswithMountFuji*, the partnership is now expanding to new frontiers—from the deep ocean to outer space, and even a joint lunar mission. Harnessing the synergistic potential of the “3Ts”—Tourism, Trade, and Technology—will further propel both nations toward shared prosperity.

Launch of the India–Japan STI Exchange Year

On January 19, 2025, H.E. Dr. S. Jaishankar, Honorable Exter-

nal Affairs Minister of India, and H.E. Takeshi Iwaya, Honorable Foreign Minister of Japan, jointly announced the designation of 2025–26 as the **India–Japan Year of Science, Technology and Innovation Exchange**. This commemorates the 40th anniversary of the first Memorandum of Understanding between India and Japan on S&T cooperation, signed in 1985.

The curtain-raiser event saw the participation of high-level dignitaries H.E. Dr. Jitendra Singh Honorable Minister of State (Independent Charge S&T, India), H.E. Mr. Sibi George (Ambassador of India to Japan), H.E. Mr. Kiuchi Minoru (Honorable Minister of State for S&T Policy, Japan), and H.E. Ms. Toshiko Abe (Honorable Minister, MEXT, Japan). More than 170 delegates attended, including deputy ministers from MEXT, director generals of S&T ministries, and presidents of leading institutions such as JAXA, NIMS, and JISTEC. Leaders of Indian S&T associations in Japan, senior government officials, and research scholars were also present—demonstrating a shared seriousness in deepening both horizontal and vertical STI exchanges.

A historic moment of the year was the unveiling of a bust of Nobel Laureate Sir C. V. Raman at Shimane University, highlighting the mutual respect both countries hold for scientific pioneers, and Science & Technology of each other.

Ongoing and Emerging Collaborations

The longstanding India–Japan S&T cooperation continues to gain momentum. Initiatives such as the Indian Beamline at KEK, LUPEX space collaboration, DST–JSPS and ICSSR–JSPS research programs, and DST–JST Joint Labs are being extended in both scope and duration.

New collaborative avenues are also opening up. The coming year is expected to feature more joint research calls—particularly in health sciences—through partnerships between DST–ICMR and Japan’s AMED. New DST–JST joint lab models are also under discussion, aiming to facilitate co-innovation and co-development through institutional cooperation.

This year, IIT Bombay and Tohoku University launched a **Joint Institute of Excellence (JIE)** to offer joint academic and research programs. Similarly, IIT Hyderabad and Shimane University established a **Joint Research Centre**. These pioneering models are expected to inspire more institutions to follow suit, marking a new beginning in reciprocal academic and research exchanges.

The premier Japanese research institutes such as NIMS, AIST, RIKEN, and JAMSTEC continue to offer opportunities for Indian researchers to join their ecosystems as postdoctoral fellows or through other programs. Significantly, Japan’s JST launched the **LOTUS Program** this year to host 300 Indian researchers for up to one year, fostering STI immer-

sion. This complements existing efforts such as the SAKURA Science Program. From India’s side, the Department of Science and Technology (DST) and Ministry of Education plan to reciprocate by inviting Japanese students for exposure visits to Indian S&T ecosystems. These visits will formally commence this year after successful pilots conducted in 2024.

There is a need to establish more platforms to accelerate collaboration in emerging sectors such as quantum technologies, high-performance computing, digital transformation and AI, green energy, ocean technologies, and critical minerals. The focus this year will be to fast-track joint projects across the entire STI ecosystem, including start-ups and industry-level collaborations.

Let-us join hands with our actions

As members of the scientific communities in India and Japan, we all have a vital role to play in operationalizing these ambitious efforts. By connecting researchers, catalyzing innovation, and fostering co-creation, we can ensure that this landmark year in India–Japan STI relations delivers lasting, measurable impact—not just for our two nations, but for the global scientific community.

Let us collectively commit to making the **India–Japan Year of Science, Technology and Innovation Exchange** truly historic, with both planning and action.

Exploring Nonlinear Optical Phenomena in Quantum Materials

Dr. Babu Baijnath Prasad

ISSP, University of Tokyo
bbprasad@issp.u-tokyo.ac.jp

Babu Baijnath Prasad is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the Institute for Solid State Physics (ISSP), University of Tokyo. His current research focuses on nonlinear optical phenomena in quantum materials, particularly second-order responses such as second-harmonic generation (SHG) and the bulk photovoltaic effect (BPVE), with an emphasis on their deep connections to quantum geometry and electronic structure.

Introduction

Quantum materials are a class of substances that exhibit unusual and exciting phenomena, such as superconductivity (flowing electricity without resistance), topological phases (conducting electricity only on their surfaces or edges), and strong electron correlations (where interactions between electrons give rise to novel effects). These materials have transformed our understanding of physics and offer a foundation for future technologies [1].

When these quantum materials are exposed to intense light, they can generate an electric polarization (P) or a current ($J = dP/dt$) that does not increase in a simple, direct way with the light's electric field (E). Instead, the response becomes nonlinear—meaning it depends on the electric field in more complex ways, such as higher-order terms (second order: E^2 , third order: E^3 , and so on) [2,3]. These nonlinear optical effects are a key area of study in condensed matter physics, as they are fundamental to many modern optical technologies. Among these effects, Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) and the Bulk Photovoltaic Effect (BPVE) have garnered considerable attention over the past decades [4,5,6].

Toward the later stages of my Ph. D. at National Taiwan University, my research shifted to exploring these nonlinear optical effects. I was particularly interested in understand-

ing light-matter interactions at the lowest nonlinear order (i.e., second order: E^2). My work focused on two key phenomena: SHG, where the material emits light at twice the frequency of the incoming light, and BPVE, where light generates an electric current without the need for a p-n junction, unlike conventional solar cells. These effects not only have promising technological applications but also serve as powerful tools to probe the inner workings of quantum materials—specifically, how their nonlinear optical responses are influenced by the geometric properties of the associated electronic wavefunctions (*wavefunction* – a mathematical function which is considered to contain the entire information of a system).

What make SHG and BPVE particularly fascinating are their sensitivity to the geometry of quantum systems, the way electrons are arranged and how their wave-like behavior is shaped in a material. This “quantum geometry” includes subtle features like how electronic states twist and spread out, which cannot be seen directly but influence how the material behaves. Understanding these hidden structures offers deeper insight into material properties and guides the design of next-generation optical and electronic devices. This research path led me to my current position as a postdoctoral researcher at the Institute for Solid State Physics (ISSP), University of Tokyo, where I continue to explore these exciting phenomena.

Methodology

To investigate how materials respond to light, I employ first-principles simulations based on density functional theory (DFT), a quantum mechanical method where the electron density forms the foundation for predicting material properties [7,8]. These simulations (e.g., using OpenMX package [9,10]) allow me to understand how electrons behave within a material and how the material may respond to external stimuli such as light or electric fields.

In crystals, which are made up of repeating units of atoms, electrons move in patterns that reflect the periodic structure of the material. In conventional electronic structure calculations for crystals, Bloch functions are commonly used because they naturally describe the periodic behavior of electrons. These Bloch functions $\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$, labeled by band index n [band – a perceived “continuum” of electron (with coordinate \mathbf{r}) energies due to the presence of a sea of electrons moving in a field set up by the atoms in the crystal] and crystal momentum \mathbf{k} [in the reciprocal space, *reciprocal space* – a complementary space to that corresponding to the actual (x, y, z) coordinate system (also called the *real space*) obtained through a certain mathematical operation known as the *Fourier transform*], can be written as

$$\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r})u_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$$

where $u_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the periodic part of the Bloch function that satisfies the periodicity of the crystal lattice. It can be expressed as

$$u_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r})\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$$

These functions provide a global picture of electron behavior throughout the crystal but are not well suited for understanding what happens in specific regions of the material. To better capture such local, real-space properties, one can transform these delocalized Bloch functions into localized Wannier functions. A Wannier function $w_n(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R})$ centered in the unit cell at lattice vector \mathbf{R} and associated with band n , can be written in terms of the Bloch functions $\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ as

$$w_n(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{R})\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$$

in a discrete representation of a grid of N \mathbf{k} points in the reciprocal space, or in the continuum limit as

$$w_n(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}) = \frac{V}{2\pi^3} \int_{\text{BZ}} \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{R})\psi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})d^3k$$

Here, V is the volume of the real-space primitive cell. Think of this as zooming in to focus on a small area in the material, where the electron behavior is more localized and easier to study. For a clear schematic illustration of both Bloch and Wannier functions, see Figure 1 of Ref. [11]. Wannier functions help us understand how electrons behave in specific regions of a material, which is essential for studying materials with complex or unique electronic properties [12].

In addition to this, Wannier functions provide a way of reducing the overall computational cost of electronic structure calculations. As mentioned previously, Bloch functions are spread out (or delocalized) across the entire crystal, implying that they require detailed information at many \mathbf{k} points in the reciprocal space to accurately capture electronic properties. This dense sampling increases computational cost significantly, especially for large or complex systems. Additionally, working with delocalized functions results in large data sets and complicated matrix elements, which demand more memory and processing power during simulations. Owing to the localized nature of Wannier functions, the electronic properties can be captured using fewer \mathbf{k} points and smaller, simpler matrices. Once Wannier functions are constructed from a limited set of Bloch data, they allow efficient interpolation of electronic bands and other properties throughout the reciprocal space. This dramatically reduces both the time and computational resources needed for simulations, making it possible to study large systems or perform detailed analyses that would be too costly with Bloch functions alone. A simple workflow showing the procedure of using the Bloch and Wannier functions to study SHG and BPVE is shown in Figure 1.

Results Summary

By using this approach, we can simulate the behavior of the material in detail, allowing us to predict its response to light and gain insights into its internal structure and electronic properties. We applied this method to study the second-order nonlinear optical effects in bismuth ferrite (BiFeO_3) [13]. BiFeO_3 was chosen for our study as it is a ferroelectric material [*ferroelectricity* – the effect of reversibly changing the electric polarization by applying an external electric field] that also exhibits magnetic properties. The ferroelectric nature in this material originates from its non-centrosymmetric structure [*non-*

centrosymmetry – a lack of center of symmetry in the structure implying that when the structure is inverted through a point, an identical copy of the structure cannot be obtained].

Fig. 1 A simple workflow to calculate nonlinear optical properties using the OpenMX-Wannier90 Interface.

We showed that magnetism-induced non-linear optical effects manifest in BiFeO_3 . Our study displays that magnetism can strongly affect and control nonlinear optical properties in BiFeO_3 . In particular, the SHG signal significantly increases and can be controlled by changing the direction of magnetization [*magnetization* – the spin magnetic moment (net spin of unpaired electrons) per unit volume of a material, which can change in response to an external magnetic field]. This also makes it possible to detect changes in the material’s internal spin order. Additionally, BiFeO_3 shows strong BPVEs.

These results help us understand how such kinds of materials could be used in future technologies, such as highly efficient solar cells or new types of light-based electronics [14,15].

Future Directions

Nonlinear optical phenomena, deeply rooted in the quantum geometry of wavefunctions, offer a rich playground for both fundamental discoveries and technological innovations. My research combines first-principles calculations, Wannier interpolation techniques, and quantum geometric analysis to en-

hance our understanding of optical and electronic phenomena in quantum materials.

These nonlinear optical effects have important real-world applications. They are key to developing faster optical communication systems, more efficient solar energy technologies through the bulk photovoltaic effect, and enhanced imaging techniques used in medicine and materials science. By deepening our understanding of these phenomena, we aim to contribute to technologies that can transform energy, communication, and sensing industries.

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Life of Inconel 718 under cyclic loading: experiments and modelling

Mohit M. Ludhwani
NIMS, Tsukuba, Japan
mohit1031996@gmail.com

A PhD student at the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Madras, India, currently at the National Institute of Materials Science (NIMS), Japan, under International Cooperative Graduate Program (ICGP). His PhD research involves understanding the fatigue behaviour of the nickel-based superalloy Inconel 718 and the evolution of back stress during changes in strain path. Alongside these experiments, his research focuses on developing a crystal plasticity model to predict the alloy's fatigue response.

Introduction

Superalloys are high-temperature materials widely employed in the aerospace, oil and gas, chemical, and nuclear industries due to their exceptional mechanical strength and superior resistance to oxidation and corrosion. These alloys are often used in components exposed to harsh environments and subjected to complex, multiaxial loading conditions [1]. Among them, Inconel 718 (IN718), a nickel-based superalloy, is utilised in jet engine components such as compressor discs, turbine blades, and shafts, as illustrated in Fig. 1, which shows a schematic of a jet engine with the various alloys used in different parts. The excellent high-temperature mechanical properties are due to the complex microstructure of IN718. The microstructure of IN718 comprises a face centered cubic (FCC) crystal γ phase matrix strength-

ened primarily by fine, disk-shaped γ'' (Ni_3Nb) precipitates with $D0_{22}$ body centered tetragonal (BCT) crystal structure approximately 20–30 nm in diameter and 5–6 nm in thickness—accounting for 15–20% of the volume fraction [2]. Additionally, spherical γ' ($\text{Ni}_3(\text{Al}, \text{Ti})$) precipitates, δ phase (Ni_3Nb), carbides, and Laves phase contribute to the overall response of IN718. Among these, γ'' precipitates are the dominant strengthening phase, critically influencing the alloy's deformation behavior.

During service, jet engine components experience cyclic loading due to engine startup and shutdown cycles, making fatigue a dominant failure mechanism. The fatigue behaviour of IN718 is marked by several distinctive features, including Bauschinger effect - a phenomenon in metals where the yield stress decreases upon load reversal - and a cyclic stress response,

Figure 1 Schematic of a typical jet engine component with its material composition.

Figure 2 Representative volume element (RVE).

typically involving initial cyclic hardening followed by gradual cyclic softening till failure. Cyclic softening refers to the reduction in the maximum stress attained during successive fatigue cycles. The fatigue responses are significantly affected by the microstructure of IN718.

Effect of microstructure on fatigue of IN718 alloy

The cyclic softening behaviour is often attributed to the precipitates, specifically the ordered γ'' , present in the alloy. The coherent γ'' precipitates are continuously sheared by the forward and backward movement of dislocations (which are line defects in a crystal formed in response to an external stress leading to deformation) under cyclic load, resulting in loss of strengthening ability of the precipitates, eventually leading to softening. In addition to γ'' precipitates other microstructure features such as the crystal grain size of the matrix phase, the character of the grain boundaries in between them, and morphology, which also affect the fatigue response. It is observed that these features can act as possible crack initiation points. This leads to scatter in the fatigue life of these materials. Interestingly, the same microstructures of the same material result in different fatigue lives, although subjected to similar loading conditions. Many fatigue tests are required to understand the effect of the microstructure on fatigue life. Therefore, incorporating microstructure information through fatigue testing is time-consuming and costly [3]. Hence, developing

fatigue life prediction models is necessary. Empirical fatigue life prediction models such as Coffin-Manson and Basquin do not account for variability in the microstructure. While these models are useful for capturing general trends, they fail to account for the influence of grain size, precipitate morphology, and grain boundary characteristics. To overcome these limitations, crystal plasticity-based models can be employed [2,4], providing a framework that directly links microstructural features to mechanical response. In addition to incorporating microstructural information, these models also need to consider cyclic softening by accounting for precipitate shearing mechanisms.

My present work aims to enhance the understanding of fatigue behaviour in IN718 by integrating experimental investigations with microstructure-sensitive crystal plasticity modelling. Strain-controlled low-cycle fatigue (LCF) tests were conducted under various loading conditions to characterize the cyclic response and associated microstructural evolution. The experimental results were used to calibrate and validate a crystal plasticity-based framework. Cyclic softening is introduced in the model through a statistical approach based on slip irreversibility (a measure of the non-recoverable plastic deformation during cycling loading), which also accounts for precipitate shearing. This integrated methodology provides a more reliable framework for predicting the fatigue response of IN718.

Crystal plasticity modelling

Crystal plasticity is a micromechanics-based modelling framework used to describe the deformation behaviour of crystalline materials by explicitly accounting for their internal crystallographic structure. Unlike conventional plasticity models, crystal plasticity considers deformation as a result of dislocation slip along specific crystallographic planes and directions, making it highly effective for capturing anisotropy, texture evolution, and grain-level heterogeneity in polycrystalline materials. The model's core involves the decomposition of the deformation gradient into elastic and plastic parts, with plastic deformation governed by the activity of multiple slip systems. A representative volume element (RVE) is commonly used to apply crystal plasticity at the polycrystalline scale.

Figure 3 (a) Comparison of simulated (first cycle) hysteresis and experimental hysteresis loop for 1%, 1.6% and 2% strain amplitude. (b) Maximum stress versus number of cycles, experimental and simulation results. σ is stress and ϵ is strain.

Representative volume element (RVE)

A RVE is a small, statistically representative section of the microstructure that includes sufficient grains to capture the material's overall behaviour. Each grain within the RVE is assigned a crystallographic orientation and follows the crystal plasticity constitutive laws.

The RVE can be generated synthetically using different approaches. This work uses DREAM3D software to generate the RVE by incorporating initial microstructural information such as grain size and orientation obtained from electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD). The RVE generated for the present study is illustrated in Fig. 2. Macroscopic stress-strain behaviour can be analyzed by simulating mechanical loading on the RVE while examining local phenomena such as strain localisation, back stress evolution, and dislocation accumulation.

Crystal plasticity framework

The Hutchinson type equation for relating the stress-strain at the slip system (α) level in crystal plasticity is shown in equation (1). Different terms in the equation can be modified to incorporate different deformation-related phenomena. The evolution equation for dislocation density (ρ^α), back stress (χ^α) and critical resolved stress (CRSS, g^α) at the slip system level is used in the present study. The Ohno-Wang type equation is employed in modelling the evolution of back stress, as expressed in equation (2). The evolution of CRSS is used to incor-

porate the cyclic softening, in the case of fatigue of IN718, as shown in equations (3) and (4).

$$\dot{\gamma}^\alpha = \dot{\gamma}_0 \left| \frac{\tau^\alpha - \chi^\alpha}{g^\alpha} \right|^n \text{sgn}(\tau^\alpha - \chi^\alpha) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\chi}^\alpha = C\dot{\gamma}^\alpha - D\dot{\gamma}^\alpha \chi^\alpha \quad (2)$$

$$g^\alpha = g_{ss}^\alpha + g_{hp}^\alpha + g_\rho^\alpha + g_{ppt}^\alpha \quad (3)$$

$$g_{ppt}^\alpha = g_{\gamma'}^\alpha + g_{c,\gamma''}^\alpha \sqrt{\hat{f}^\alpha \hat{r}_{ppt}^\alpha} \quad (4)$$

Where $\dot{\gamma}_0$ is the reference shear rate, τ^α is the resolved shear stress, and C and D are the parameters of the Frederick-Armstrong model. In this work, CRSS(g^α)—which governs how much stress is needed to activate slip in each crystallographic system—is modelled as a sum of contributions from solid solution strengthening (g_{ss}^α), grain size effects (Hall-Petch, g_{hp}^α), dislocation density (g_ρ^α) and precipitate (g_{ppt}^α). To capture cyclic softening, we explicitly model the progressive shearing of these γ'' precipitates during fatigue. This is achieved by introducing an evolution law for the precipitate contribution, which depends on the effective volume fraction (\hat{f}^α) and radius (\hat{r}^α) of γ'' precipitate, both of which degrade over time. Their evolution is described using a decay function driven by slip irreversibility.

While the rest of the crystal plasticity framework, like the evolution equation of dislocation density (ρ^α), is based on well-established models in the

literature [5], the current work extends it by embedding this softening mechanism. As a result, the model provides improved predictive capability for the fatigue response of IN718.

Results

The fully reverse strain-controlled low-cycle fatigue test has been performed on IN718. The experimental results are used to calibrate the key material parameters required in the crystal plasticity framework. These calibrated parameters are then employed without further adjustment to predict the material response under different loading conditions.

As a preliminary step, the parameters for the developed model are obtained from experimental data available in the literature [6]. Initial comparisons between the experimental and simulated responses, as shown in Figure 3, demonstrate good agreement, underscoring the model's predictive capability. Specifically, the stress-strain response from the first cycle at a strain amplitude of 1.6% is used to extract the initial set of parameters. The evolution equations incorporated in the framework are then employed to simulate the fatigue behaviour at other strain amplitudes and for the experiments conducted in the present study. The observed consistency between experimental results and simulation predictions validates the accuracy and robustness of the proposed model.

Future work

Dislocation–precipitate interactions in IN718 are modelled using a simplified, statistical approach.

However, precipitate shearing gradually evolves during cyclic loading and influences material response over time. Incorporating this evolving behaviour can improve the accuracy of fatigue modelling. Additionally, the present work is focused on room temperature conditions. Still, the findings and framework can be extended to high-temperature applications where changes in dislocation activity and precipitate stability are expected to play a significant role. These future developments aim to better understand the IN718's performance under realistic service conditions.

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ISAJ Hokkaido Symposium 2024

Collaborative Solutions for a Sustainable World

Conveners: Dr. Amrutha A. S., Dr. Shivakumar K. I. and Dr. Ravindra Raut, Hokkaido University, Japan

Following the success of the 14th Annual Symposium of ISAJ in 2023, the Hokkaido Chapter of ISAJ organized a Hokkaido region symposium in CRIS Building of Hokkaido University Sapporo campus on December 13, 2024, as ISAJ Hokkaido 2024 Symposium, supported by the university and its Research Institute of Electronic Science (RIES) and Institute for Chemical Reaction Design and Discovery (ICReDD).

Themed “Collaborative Solutions for a Sustainable World,” the symposium emphasized the importance of international collaboration in addressing global challenges through science and technology. This symposium was led by Dr. Amrutha A.S., Dr. Shivakumar K.I. and Dr. Ravindra Raut of Hokkaido University as conveners. The symposium drew strong participation from Indian and Japanese researchers - particularly young scientists in Hokkaido - and reflected ISAJ’s ongoing commitment to highlighting contributions of a thriving Indian researcher community in this region. The presence of high-level university leadership and Indian embassy representation reinforced the importance of the occasion.

The symposium opened with welcoming remarks from convener Dr. Amrutha A. S. This was followed by a keynote address by Dr. Aya Takahashi, Vice President of Hokkaido University. She highlighted the university’s deepening collaboration with Indian researchers and growing Indian scholar community on the campus. Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar (Embassy of India, Tokyo), Prof. Kuniharu Ijio (Director, RIES, Hokkaido University), Dr. Sunil Kaul (ISAJ Chairman) and Dr. Alok Singh (Vice Chairman, ISAJ) added their thoughts, applauding the growing Indo-Japanese scientific bridge.

The symposium delivered a diverse and intellectually stimulating program which had 3 Plenary Lectures, 3 Invited Talks, 4 Talks by Young Researchers, 5 General Oral Presentations and 24 Poster Presentations. These presentations spanned key topics, such as Mechanochemistry (Prof. Hajime Ito),

High-Energy Physics (Dr. Arindam Das), Advanced Materials & Catalysis (Prof. Shin-ichiro Noro, Dr. Nobuya Tsuji), and Nanomaterials & Computational Chemistry (Prof. Vasudevan Biju, Dr. Pinku Nath, Dr. Kiyonori Takahashi).

The afternoon poster session buzzed with energy, providing opportunities for deeper engagement among early-career scientists. Four posters were chosen for Best Poster Awards: Jayaprakash Jayashankar for his poster entitled “Exploring the Potential Role of Wakame-Based Bioactive Compounds as Anti-Obesity Agents: ...,” Priya Saha for her poster “Defluorinative Cross Couplings of Tri-fluoromethyl Arenes by Copper Photoredox Catalysis,” Satoshi Matsutani for “Developing a Conformational Sampling Method For Transition State Structures With Varying Reaction Centers” and Aneesha S. L. for “Interaction Between Phenolic Acids and Bovine Hemoglobin: Multi-Spectroscopic and Computational Studies.”

The Best Oral Presentation Award went to two young scientists: Nazmul Shaikh for his talk on “Designing Co single site atom doped ZrO₂ for selective CO₂ conversion to CO” and Aravind Kandaswamy for “Shortwave-infrared cyanine fluorescent probes: A new approach for deep tissue molecular imaging.” Convener Dr. Ravindra Raut closed the symposium by thanking all the attendees, hosts and ISAJ’s executive team.

This symposium, held shortly after ISAJ’s 15th Annual Symposium in Tokyo, highlights the rapidly growing community of Indian researchers in every region of Japan, and ISAJ’s strategic efforts to realize its greater potential. With continued support from Hokkaido University and the Indian diplomatic mission in Japan, the event affirmed the mutual vision of nurturing sustainable science through collaboration. ISAJ’s presence in Hokkaido continues to grow, providing an increasingly vital platform for emerging scientists to contribute to global innovation. [based on reporting by Prof. P.K. Hashim]

ISAJ Hokkaido Symposium 2024

From left to right: Convener Dr. Amrutha, Vice President of Hokkaido University Prof. Takahashi, Embassy of India Dr. Panwar, RIES Director Prof. Ijiro, ISAJ Chairman Dr. Kaul and ISAJ Vice Chairman Dr. Singh speak during the opening session.

Opening session

A technical session

Dr. Hashim conducts a special session

Lively poster session

Lively discussions during the poster session!

ISAJ Hokkaido Symposium 2024 held on 13th December 2024
in Hokkaido University campus
(report and pictures inside)

Editors

Alok Singh, Ph.D.

National Institute for Materials Science, Japan
quasi.sci@gmail.com

Aaditya Manjanath, Ph.D.

National Institute for Materials Science, Japan
manjanath.aaditya@nims.go.jp

About ISAJ

The Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ) is a Non-Profit Organization (NPO) aimed at networking and promoting Science and Technology Cooperation between India and Japan.

Contact Us:

Feel free to write to us:

For any information about ISAJ and membership: chairman@isaj.jp

ISAJ mailing list (join): isaj-community@googlegroups.com

Visit us on the web at <https://isaj.jp>

Postal address: Nagakuni Dai 3-24,
Tsuchiura-shi, Ibaraki-ken, 300-0810 Japan

Phone: (+81) (0)90-9688-1186

Visit us at <https://isaj.jp>

